

The Proposal for a New Fiscal Governance in the EU: An Overlapping Overhaul¹

Wim Moesen¹

1. Professor Emeritus, KU Leuven, Department of Economics

1. Introduction

Early 2020, just before the corona calamity, the new European Commission launched a broad consultation round on the adequacy of the fiscal rules in the EU. In the meantime, during four consecutive budget years the stringent fiscal rules were suspended, invoking the general escape clause.

In November 2022 the Commission communicated orientations for a reform of the EU economic governance framework. In this policy paper the new proposals are assessed against the current ‘numerology’ of a deficit ceiling of 3 pct. (of GDP) and the prescription to reduce the debt ratio to 60 pct. in the medium term.

Two flagships stand out in the communication.

- (i) The elaboration of a fiscal-structural medium-term plan, tailored and agreed by each member state, intended to be

country-specific. In other words, one size does not fit all.

- (ii) The emphasis on one operational indicator, namely the net expenditure trajectory, designed for and committed by each member state.

These new proposals fit into correcting the earlier claims that the current design lacks simplicity, transparency, enforceability, credibility and ownership by the internal governments.

Unfortunately, the new proposals do not explicitly address the concern that public investments should not be pinched in the new architecture. Prominent economists favor a rehabilitation of the golden financing rule with a preferential accounting treatment of necessary and valuable public investments.

2. What is the Commission Proposing

The central element is the medium-term fiscal-structural plan that will be elaborated

¹ Thanks to Nadine De Corte and Anouk Vermeyen for valuable assistance help.

for each member state. The Commission ambitions to create a ‘simpler and more transparent’ design for the fiscal governance. Also the broader macroeconomic surveillance will be integrated in the new architecture. For ease of exposition we will only focus on the budgetary rules. The Macroeconomic Imbalance Procedure (MIP), the European Semester and also the tedious debate on a Central Fiscal Capacity will not be treated explicitly.

For the member states with a high or medium debt level, the national plan should ensure a sustainable gradual debt reduction path. While preserving structural reforms and the necessary public investments, in particular those instrumental to meet the twin green and digital targets.

Each national plan will have a country-specific drawing, but within a common fiscal governance framework. The procedure can be summarized as follows. As a preliminary step the Commission is entitled to rely on a professional risk-based methodology to identify three categories of member states: those with a high, a moderate and a low ‘public debt challenge’. The methodology will be state-of-the-art and together with the underlying data made available. Based on these findings the Commission puts forward reference adjustment paths tailored for each member state.

The next step is a vivid interaction with the member states. They are responsible for the draft of their own medium-term fiscal-structural plan. Their efforts take into account their own concerns for desirable structural reforms and public investments when elaborating their debt adjustment trajectory. The plan covers in principle four years but can be extended up to seven years. The

submission of the plan is preceded by in-depth technical dialogues with the Commission.

Subsequently the plan will be adopted by the Council upon a positive Commission assessment. Annual budgets will commit to follow the agreed fiscal trajectory and ensure that debt will start converging to prudent levels within the adjustment period.

Another flagship of the proposal is the emphasis on one operational indicator, namely the ‘net nationally financed expenditure’ path agreed with the member state. This move towards a ‘simple’ expenditure rule requires a clear definition and calculation of the concept of net expenditures. In essence the norm encompasses all primary expenditures. The interest bill on the government debt is thus excluded. The concept limits the perimeter to nationally financed expenditures. E.g. grants from the European Recovery and Resilience Facility are left out. Also discretionary revenues stay aside. In order to mitigate somewhat the cyclical effects of the budget, the outlays for unemployment compensation are also exempted. As it stands now public investments remain included in the reference concept. This is an unfortunate attitude as will be indicated later on.

For each member state the medium-term plan would be translated in annual expenditure ceilings, deemed to be the pivotal indicator for the fiscal surveillance.

3. General Principles

As a general principle it will not be possible for member states to revise their plans. However, in the case of objective circumstances an ‘exceptional circumstances clause’ would allow for temporary deviations from the medium-term fiscal path. Objective in the sense of extraordinary circumstances outside

the control of the member state and with a major impact on its public finances. For a common substantial external shock, the general escape clause would be maintained to deal with a severe economic downturn.

It should be noticed that the Excessive Deficit Procedure (EDP) would be retained in the new proposal. The so-called deficit-based EDP remains unchanged for the breaches of the 3 pct. (of GDP) reference value. The debt-based EDP would be strengthened.

- For those member states with a substantial public debt challenge departures from the agreed fiscal path would by default result in the opening of the EDP.
- For member states with a moderate public debt challenge, departures could still lead to the opening of the EDP, if assessed as giving rise to ‘gross errors’.

A frequent critique on the current fiscal guidance is that the actual rules are not enforceable. New enforcement mechanisms are thus proposed by the Commission. First financial sanctions would be made more effective by lowering their amounts. Secondly, the European authority would work on stronger reputational sanctions. Thirdly, EU financing could be suspended for member states that benefit from grants and other financial assistance programmes from the EU. It remains questionable whether the enforceability will increase in the proposed scheme and ‘work’ where applied on the field. The new proposals suffer at the outset from a greater role of ‘bilateralism’ in the interactions with the surveillance authority. In such negotiations some member states may benefit from an unequal political weight. To mitigate somehow this potential problem, the Commission puts forward the installation of a

professional Independent Fiscal Institution (IFI) in each member state.

4. Assessment and Reflections

Vast empirical research, long before corona, reveals that countries with sound public finances and low debt levels benefit from two budgetary practices. (i) They are familiar with multi-annual budgetary estimates. And (ii) they apply the routine of an explicit expenditure rule. The focus on the new medium-term fiscal-structural plan fits into these recommendations. In the context of issue (i) a sketchy observation indicates that in some member states a culture of ‘experts de la navigation à vue’ indeed still dominates the budgetary procedure. The drafting of the annual budget is then primarily perceived as an imposed embarrassing exercise which economizes as much as possible on time and effort from the national policy makers. The upgrading of the expenditure norm up to the level of the single surveillance indicator addresses the concern from observation (ii).

Let us briefly review the analytical underpinnings of the current numerical targets for a broader assessment of the new proposals. In the fiscal literature several waves of criticism have questioned the adequacy of the current numerical norms, initiated by the Maastricht Treaty (1992), later on prescribed in the Stability and Growth Pact (SGP, 1997, 2005) and during the sovereign debt crisis refined in the Sixpack (2011) and Twopack (2013). Is there some rationality between the 3 pct. deficit ceiling and the long run target of 60 pct. for the debt ratio?

On the theoretical level there is an internal consistency, as shown in appendix 1. Let nominal GDP, denoted as Y , growth with a trend rate g (roughly equally attributed to real growth and inflation). Assume for ease of

exposition that the ratio of the fiscal deficit to Y is a constant a . It then follows that in a steady state the debt ratio will tend towards a/g .

It appears that in the back-offices of the Maastricht Treaty a nominal growth rate g of 5 pct. a year was deemed achievable. Experiences of the mature economies in euroland, based on historical data, showed that an average public investment accounted for 3 pct. of GDP. For capital projects debt finance is admitted as future generations of taxpayers also will benefit from the productive facilities. Therefore, a deficit of 3 pct. could be defended for the medium run. Notice that in these circumstances the golden financing rule is implicitly obeyed. Plugging in these figures in the steady state formula one gets the debt ratio $b = 0.03/0.05 = 60$ pct.

The well-known 60 pct. benchmark is thus consistent with the two underlying variables g and a . But now comes the tricky issue in times of stagnation or even deflation. Given a forecast for the euro-zone, a nominal g of 4 pct. (2 pct. real growth + 2 pct. inflation), the steady state b is 75 pct. ($0.03/0.04$). And in a more morose scenario of 3 pct. nominal growth the debt ratio will tend towards 100 pct. In other words: the steady state debt ratio is a moving target.

In table 1 the steady state formula is used as a didactical device to demonstrate the great volatility of the debt ratio. If one also allows to alter the deficit ratio with one percent in either direction, then the highest and lowest debt ratio moves between 33 and 100 pct. Indeed in the steady state the debt ratio is a moving target.

Moreover one should remember that in the current practice the member states of the euro area were ordered to obey the so-called 1/20th

rule. This means that the gap between the actual debt ratio and the norm of 60 pct. should be cleared within 20 years. A country with e.g. a debt level of 140 pct. should realize a reduction of the debt rate with 4 pct. a year. For countries which are already highly indebted this stringent rule may lead to an unrealistic fiscal trajectory. This is by now recognized in the new proposal of the Commission. One size does not fit all. The sustainable debt ratio is a moving target depending on more country specific characteristics: the deficit ratio, real growth, inflation, the interest rate, the share of public investment versus current expenditures, the net stock public of physical capital, the democratic burden of pensions, structural reforms,... All these elements are candidates for capture in the negotiated debt reduction path as proposed by the Commission.

Let us reflect a while on some behavioral consequences of the balanced budget rule as such. One can predict that this stringent rule will discourage the outlays for public investments. It implies that capital projects will have to be funded from current revenues. The costs of such investments are no longer spread over all the generations of the payers who benefit from these productive facilities. It is expected that such a rule delays and diminishes public investments.

A balanced budget is at odds with standard economic principles. Furthermore, imagine a hypothetical situation where all countries would adopt a balanced budget for the total public expenditures. Deficits and borrowing would disappear. In the long run the public debt level would tend to zero. This implies that also the riskless interest rate on public debt would no longer be available as a reference rate for the standard finance theory.

The panic of the fiscal policy makers during the sovereign debt crisis (2010 – 2014) has inspired a more mitigated version: ‘the balanced structural budget’. The nominal budget is then corrected for the fiscal impact of the business cycle and one-off expenditures/revenues. But these data are not directly observable in the public accounts. They require an ‘external’ calculation. But how can one in real-time estimate the output gap, i.e. the deviation from the actual versus the potential output? Even in retrospect there is much confusion and revisions ex post. In other words the balanced budget is an Unidentified Flying Object (UFO) and thus difficult to enforce credibly. Most economists did not favor this opaque concept which is now rightly dismissed in the Commission proposal.

5. A Rehabilitation of the Golden Financing Rule

The golden financing rule offers a solid financing prescription for the public sector. Current expenditures (public consumption, transfers, interest payments on the public debt...) should be financed by regular receipts (taxes, social security contributions, levies) which provide a recurrent stream of revenues. Public borrowing is not allowed for the current account of the budget. Public investments, on the contrary, are entitled to be financed by public debt. In economic reasoning it is argued that in their valuable use benefits the citizens for several years to come. Through borrowing, also the cost (mainly interest charges) are also spread over future cohorts of taxpayers. As a metaphor to a private household it is recommended that parents should not borrow money to spend on restaurants or vacations. For the construction of a house, however, borrowing is well conceded.

In the decade before the corona crisis budgetary austerity has pinched our public investments. Indeed it is less difficult to postpone necessary investment from a pure political point of view. As such, most EU-countries have badly neglected public investments. Gross public investments hardly compensate for the deterioration of the existing capital stock. A case in point is Belgium where the net fixed capital stock had gradually decreased from 50 pct. of GDP in 1995 to 37 pct. in 2015. This is significantly below the next neighbour countries. In 2015 the public net capital stock stood at 46 pct. in Germany, in France it was 55 pct. and remarkably 62 pct. in the Netherlands.

The golden rule locates the need for budgetary discipline where it belongs: on the current account. In the concept of a dual budget government investments are registered on a capital account. For several decades Belgium has adhered successfully to a dual budget. In fact, the dual budget was abandoned in 1975, in the aftermath of the Yom Kippur war (1973) and the first oil crisis with auto-less Sundays. The concept is still applied in Belgium in the context of the municipalities.

It is often claimed that it is difficult to operationalize the golden rule. Indeed, the usual definitions of current expenditures leave elbow room for opportunistic interpretations to erode the rule. Some policy makers who were involved in the drafting of the Maastricht Treaty, claim that originally they favored the golden rule, but they were reluctant to enshrine it in the Treaty on an explicit basis due precisely to the classification difficulties. Nowadays this issue is less prominent. The European system of national accounts identifies actually in its decimal codification of public expenditures the category 7: fixed material assets. This is a quite narrow

definition of public investment but which provides a workable starting point. The point is that on the balance sheet of the government sector the new assets are matched with public debt at the liabilities side. At least if the public investments are well chosen. We will address this issue in a following paragraph.

In the fiscal literature prominent economists have since a long time pleaded for 'Improving the SGP through a proper accounting of public investment' (Blanchard, O. and F. Giavazzi , 2004). Also professor Jacques Drèze, Belgium's best known economist, has fiercely defended such an approach (Drèze, J. and A. Durré, 2014). In his seminal paper one reads the following quote "One must always distinguish the current account from the capital account. The standard rule for a nominal deficit/GDP ratio computed from the sum of the current and capital account is thus misleading".

The recent energy crisis with supply shortages and price hikes has triggered the public conscience in the EU that the transformation from fossil fuels to renewable energy constitutes a project of immediate urgency. This vast project of the EU requires lots of money and public investments. How to select the investment projects which are eligible for (co)financing by public debt?

From an economic point of view two criteria stand out: the macroeconomic Keynesian multiplier effect in the shorter run and the microeconomic Pigouvian program effect itself in the longer run. The superior multiplier effect of public investments – vis-à-vis other categories of public expenditures – is well documented. The Pigouvian microeconomic program effect may invite some clarification. A.C. Pigou, a colleague of the more flamboyant J.M. Keynes at Cambridge, in his analytical work has tackled

mainly microeconomic themes. He is best known for his seminal book 'The economics of welfare' (1923). In later editions he introduced the concept of spill-over (or indirect) effects, which may be positive (benefit) or negative (cost) externalities.

A simple example may clarify the difference in approach between the Keynesian macroeconomic multiplier effect of spending and the Pigouvian microeconomic program effect. Imagine a public investment project, e.g. a bridge without access roads. The multiplier effect will propagate as expected. All labor and material inputs will be paid and the purchasing power will be spent further in the economy. Consider by contrast a useful bridge which 'solves' the congestion problem across a river. Commuters will save on their waiting times, pollution will be lower and safety may increase while accidents diminish. Pigou articulates such contributions to the welfare of the community in terms of external benefits and costs. And this stretches out over a longer time of beneficial use.

Next to the short run macroeconomic multiplier effect, policy makers should also assess the long run beneficial effect for society. The selection of the suitable investment projects can then be based on a more formal cost-benefit analysis. Such a more sophisticated exercise precisely envisages the Pigouvian externalities in the calculation of the net societal benefit.

6. Enhanced Role for the Independent Fiscal Institutions (IFIs)

To increase ownership and transparency at the national level, an Independent Fiscal Institution (IFI) in each member state will be endorsed with an enhanced role. It is expected

that the national IFI will be instrumental in drafting the medium-term fiscal-structural plan of each member state. At the core of its professional competence, the IFI should ex-ante assess all the economic and budgetary forecasts, produced by their national government in the context of the new common European framework. The time horizon of these macro-forecasts cover the short and medium term and also the long term assessment of the status of the public finances.

As already indicated the main mandate is to design a medium-term fiscal-structural plan which would ensure that the debt ratio will develop on ‘a credibly and continuously declining path’. In setting that adequate trajectory the impact of ‘structural reforms and public investments’ should also be assessed. These exercises require additional competences of the IFI. Next to the macro-forecasting dimensions the IFI should also master the more micro-economic methodologies for the project evaluation and management.

Are these new competences already integrated in the functioning of the IFI? Could a conflict of interest arise when the IFI is perceived as an ‘advocate’ of some specific reforms and investment prospects rather than their traditional role as an impartial ‘external’ observator (2023, EU Economic Governance Proposal Reform: Issues and Insights from EU IFIs).

These and other concerns are not clarified yet. In terms of resources these reflections suggest that in some member states additional resources are required when the IFI still needs to develop modellings for the reform impacts. Additional analysts with complementary competences can bridge the gap in capacities up to the level of the EU peers.

7. Findings of the Online Public Survey

The milestones in the timing of the revision procedure have been delayed on several occasions. As it stands now the Commission intends to forward its final proposal early in 2024. In the meantime (autumn 2021) the Commission had relaunched the revision through various channels. Interesting insights emerge from the online public survey, which was closed end December 2021, before Russia’s invasion in Ukraine.

The summary of responses was reported in a Commission staff working document (March 28, 2022). The survey summarizes responses to eleven open-ended questions on different aspects of the EU economic governance. It received 225 valid contributions from respondents in 25 different countries. The submissions from unaffiliated EU citizens and by stakeholders from academic/research institutions, thinktanks and trade unions represented two-thirds of the replies. Other contributions originated from non-governmental organizations (NGO’s) and the business sector.

The profiles of the survey participants are quite interesting. The highest contributions came from Italy (64 responses) and Belgium (37 responses). Both highly indebted countries reveal apparently greater concern about the sustainability of their public finances. Could it be that it reflects also a necessity for external budgetary discipline imposed by Europe? Germany figures as a honorable third with 31 responses. About two out of five respondents, especially those from academia and thinktanks, complemented their online survey replies with more detailed studies and papers.

As expected a large number of the survey answers called for simplification, transparency, enforceability and stronger national ownership from the current fiscal governance. The Commission staff summarized the eleven open-ended questions into six themes. On top one finds the need for higher public investment as a key EU challenge (75 pct. of the responses). They call for specific provisions in the fiscal rules to safeguard/increase overall public investments. They also suggest that preferential treatment should be granted to certain types of investment that would contribute to meeting EU-wise objectives such as climate mitigation, decarbonization and digital excellence.

At position two, respondents underline the need for a fiscal framework to ensure sustainable public finances (more than 60 pct. of the respondents). They argue for debt reduction paths that are gradual, country-specific and consistent with sustained economic growth.

To a great extent the Commission new proposal squares with this second recommendation. One size does not fit all. A country conform debt reduction trajectory is agreed, with only one simple surveillance indicator i.e. the net expenditure path “negotiated” with the member state. These are two steps forward that the structurally balanced budget is dismissed as non-observable (cfr. The UFO metaphor) and that the 1/20th rule for debt reduction is qualified as unrealistic.

The adoption of the first recommendation, promoting public investments, is on the other hand far less convincing in the Commission proposal. Of course the proposal recognizes that substantial levels of public investments are required to achieve a fair twin transition

(green and digital) and to ensure energy security. But it remains puzzling that only a few paragraphs in the proposal deal explicitly with incentivizing public investments, the top priority from the online consultation. These paragraphs can be summarized in the following quote: “These objectives call for investments by corporations and households, but also for higher public investments, backed by a good composition and quantity of public finances.” It is also remarkable that the implementation of ‘reform and investment commitments’ are lapsed together in a scarce paragraph.

It is obvious that the outlays for public investments figure in the official government debt statistics. But a preferential treatment of public investment in the deficit calculation remains to be developed. Moreover it is also evident that the golden financing rule is compatible with a net current expenditures rule.

8. Up to the Legislative Proposals and the New Fiscal Numerology

On April 26 of 2023 the Commission tabled proposals for three legislative acts to build an economic governance framework fit for the challenges ahead. What is new in the domain of fiscal governance since the reform Orientations of the Commission from 8 November 2022?

- First of all the 3% and 60% of GDP reference values for deficit and debt will remain unchanged.
- The ratio of public debt to GDP will have to be lower at the end of the period covered by the medium-term fiscal-structural plan than at the start of that period. Moreover, a minimum fiscal adjustment per year will have to

be implemented so long as the deficit remains above 3% of GDP.

- Furthermore, member states benefitting from an extended fiscal adjustment period (up to seven years) will have to deliver most of the fiscal adjustment effort the (standard) first four years covered by the extended period.
- Another aspect in the new proposals is the emphasis on compliance with the commitments of the medium-term fiscal-structural plan. For instance failure to deliver on the commitments of reform and public investment, justifying the extension period, would trigger enforcement actions.

Recently greater concerns had sadly emerged. The ongoing Ukraine-war and the geopolitical tensions required more public resources for strengthening national security and military expenditures. This on top of the twin standard targets of the energy transition away from fossil fuels towards renewable energy and the digitalization of society : business, households, health care, education, public administrations ... As a case in point the new fiscal governance should also engage in safeguarding the European green deal and the EU net-zero industry net.

Painstaking discussions, within the Econfin-council – the regular meetings of the finance ministers of the eurozone- and later with the European Parliament required lots of political negotiations and embarrassment. Admittedly, the lack of harmony between Germany and France, the two historic leading countries, did not help. Finally on Saturday, February 10th, after sixteen hours of talks, the Belgian presidency of the EU-council could proclaim ‘a deal is ours’.

Let us briefly reflect on the essence of the divergences. As already noted the new fiscal framework centers around the medium-term fiscal-structural plan, tailored for each member state. This boils down in to a ‘qualitative longer view’ debt sustainability analysis for each member state. This outcome squares with the aspirations of the medium and highly indebted countries. But in the final negotiations the ‘frugal’ member states insisted on additional numerical norms and safety margins to enforce that after the adjustment period of 4 (up to 7) years the public debt ratio should be on a “plausible and continuously declining path”.

The new fiscal governance numerology can be summarized as follows :

- Member states with a debt level above 60% should reduce the debt ratio with 0.5 percentage points (pp) per year (on average). For countries with a debt level above 90% the minimum reduction of the debt ratio is augmented to 1 pp.
- Countries with a deficit ratio that exceeds 3% are required to reduce the deficit with 0.4 pp per year if the adjustment period covers 4 years. If the adjustment trajectory is extended to 7 years, then the yearly reduction should cover at least 0.25 pp. In any case, when the deficit is below the 3%, the individual countries should strive to reach the proposed 1,5% safety margin.
- The new rules envisage a more stringent surveillance for the countries with a debt level above 60% and a deficit ratio greater than 3%. The anchor target is here the net expenditure norm tailored for each member state. Deviations from the norm are registered on a ‘control

account' with an allowed margin of 0.3 pp per single year and cumulative 0.6 pp for two years.

- When the commission and the council assess that the set of numerical norms from the preventive arm of the fiscal framework are not achieved, then the excess deficit procedure (EDP) of the corrective arm of the fiscal framework may be opened. This prescribes that a yearly 'fiscal effort' is imposed to reduce the structural deficit with 0.5 pp until it is below 3%. Countries that do not comply with the EDP can be sanctioned with a fine up to 0.05 of GDP, next to a reputation loss.

9. Summing Up

In the meantime also the geo-political context has changed substantially. Take for instance the Inflation Reduction ACT (IRA) which has stirred economic discomfort in the EU, where it is perceived as an explicit industrial endeavor under the guise of fiscal policy. The US legislation now recognizes the urgency for a federal climate change policy away from fossil fuels towards renewable energy. A muscled budget of 369 billion dollar will substantially subsidize its business sector to facilitate the transition. As an example is the promotion of electric vehicles, the IRA offers ample tax credits for consumers to support 'made in the USA'. This additional stimulus comes on top of its comparative advantage as the US is already better endowed with natural resources.

Legitimately the EU worries that these initiatives – laudable as they are in their own right – will jeopardize the level playing field with the US in terms of economic competitiveness. What can Europe do? As a first concern a green subsidy race, detrimental to the economies both in the US and the EU,

should be contained. And as a collateral damage a fierce fragmentation between the political leaders of the member states itself should be avoided.

Europe has in recent months launched several important actions: the critical materials act, the European green industry plan for the net-zero age, a hydrogen project for the EU,... They all focus on the green transformation of the industry and the digitalization of the society. Enormous public investments are required to meet somehow these targets, together with the private sector. For solid solutions in these endeavors a huge financing squeeze will emerge. Many economists still find it difficult to grasp why the Commission does not make a distinction between the investment account next to the current account in the budgets of the member states, as prescribed by the golden financing rule.

Starting with high ambition several policy makers favored at the outset of the revision exercise a complete overhaul of the existing fiscal rules. Blanchard et al. (2021) advocated a scrapping of the fiscal rules altogether, promoting fiscal standards instead. The recent proposals of the Commission do not live up to the aspiration at the high end of the spectrum. They overlap with the maintained rules of 3% (deficit rate) and 60% (target debt rate). Hopefully the medium-term fiscal-structural plan, cornerstone in the new proposals, adds value to the new design and remedies some of the shortcomings of the earlier framework. One stands out fortunately: one size no longer fits all.

Let us also endorse the Jean Monnet quote: "L'Europe se fera par les crises et sera la sommation des réponses à ses crises".

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

References

- Bardt, H. and S. Dullien, M. Huether, K. Rietzler (2020), "For a sound fiscal policy: enabling public investment", IMK Report 152.
- Blanchard, O. and F. Giavazzi (2004), "Improving the SGP through a proper accounting of public investment", CEPR Discussion Papers 4220, London.
- Blanchard, O. and D. Leigh (2013), "Growth forecast errors and fiscal multipliers", *American Economic Review*, 103 (3), 117-20.
- Blanchard, O. and L. Alvaro, J. Zettelmeyer (2021), "Redesigning EU fiscal rules: from rules to standards", Peterson Institute for International Economics (PIIE), working paper 21-1.
- Claeys, G. and Z. Darvas, A. Leandro (2016), "A proposal to revue the European Fiscal Framework". Breugel Policy Contribution 2016/07, Brussels.
- Darvas, Z. and L. Welslau, J. Zettelmeyer (2024), "Incorporating the impact of social investments and reforms in the European Union's new fiscal framework", working paper 07/2024, Breugel, Brussels.
- Drèze, J. and A. Durré (2014), "Fiscal integration and growth stimulation in Europe", *Recherches Economiques de Louvain* 2014/2, Louvain-la-Neuve.
- European Commission (2022), "Communication on the orientations for a reform of the EU economic governance framework", Brussels, November 2022.
- European Commission (2023), "Proposals for legislative actions", Brussels, April 2023.
- European Network of IFIs (2023), "EU economic governance proposal reform: issues and insights from EU IFIs".
- EU trialogue Commission-Council-Parliament (2024), "Proposal on the effective coordination of economic policies and multilaterally budgetary surveillance", Brussels, February 2024.
- Glaeser, E. and J. Poterba (2020), "Economic analysis and infrastructure investment", NBER working paper 28215, 39p.
- Keynes, J.M. (1936), "The general theory of employment, interest and money", New York, Harcourt Brace.
- Martin, Ph. Et J. Pisani-Ferry, X. Ragot (2020), "Pour une refonte du cadre budgétaire Européen, Conseil d'Analyse Economique, 63, Paris.
- Moesen, W. (2020), "Searching for a revision of the fiscal rules in the EU", KU Leuven, mimeo, 27 pages.
- Pigou, A.C. (1920), "The economics of welfare", London, Mac Millan.

Figures

Table 1. The debt ratio as a moving target

		Deficit ratio a		
		2	3	4
Nominal	4	50	75	100
growth g	5	40	60*	80
	6	33	50	66

DemoTrans is funded by the European Commission in its Horizon Europe framework (grant 101059288). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Follow us online www.democracy-transparency.eu

Follow us on Twitter [@DemoTrans](https://twitter.com/DemoTrans)

Follow us on LinkedIn www.linkedin.com/company/demotrans-project/